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Analyzing School Attachment of Secondary School Students' for Regards to Various Variables

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate whether school attachment levels of secondary school students change according to gender, class level, family income level, academic achievement, parents' age level, parents' job and parents' education level variables or not. The sample of the study consists of 382 (211 female, 171 male) students studying in 5th, 6th, 7th and 8th grades of two secondary schools in Beylikdüzü district of Istanbul in the 2019-2020 academic year. In this study, the "Personal Information Form" developed by the researcher and the "School Attachment Scale for Children and Adolescents" adapted to Turkish by Savi (2011) were used as data collection tools. T-test for binary variables and ANOVA statistical technique for multiple variables were used. According to the findings of the study, there was no significant difference between the variables of gender, academic achievement, parents' age level, mother's job, family income level and father's education level. However, A significant difference was found between the groups in the variables of the class level of the student, father's job and mother's education level. The findings were discussed and suggestions presented.

Keywords: School Attachment, Academic Achievement, Student

1. Introduction

Education is a complex process consisting of different variables. It is known that emotional processes contribute greatly to achieving educational goals during this period. The environment where the individual establishes the most relationship and interaction with others in the school. Therefore, school has a great and effective place in individuals' lives. The happier life of individuals in the future differs according to their education level (Alaca, 2011). School is the first environment where students socialize and begin to acquire the skills they need to adapt to society (Bellici, 2015). The quality of the process experienced at school affects the student's commitment to the school as they prepare the students for their future lives.

Driving students forward, the quality of the process experienced at school is one of the factors affecting student attachment to the school (Kalaycı & Özdemir, 2013). However, the school is considered successful as long as it

provides individuals to learn the subjects they need in order to be able to socialize and be happy (Yavuzer, 2002). The school, which has a great place in the development of every person and where the education and training process takes place, offers a protective environment for children. It also has the ability to reduce the likelihood of individuals exhibiting negative behaviors (Jackson & Warren, 2000). Learning is essential in developing self-actualization and competencies. Therefore, it is necessary to complete school education for the academic, personal and professional life of the individual (Garnier., Stein & Jacobs, 1997). It is necessary to establish positive relationships at school, for healthy development and adaptation to the school (Hepler, 1997). New bonds emerge with the school life, where children are separated from their families for the first time. Attachment to the school as a student's feeling of belonging to the school and embracing its goals (Finn, 1993) includes not only a simple liking or warmth, but also respect and support for the individual autonomy of the student (Goodenow, 1992). School attachment plays a protective role in students against negativities such as orientation towards negative behaviors towards school and personal inadequacy (Özdemir, 2015). Especially the communication of students based on trust with their parents will reflect positively on their bonding. Attachment creates a strong emotional system with the emotional bonds of individuals to the people they care about (Bowlby, 2012). Students' negative behaviors at school and the attitudes of school stakeholders (administrator, teacher and student) about the problems they experience have positive or negative effects on school attachment. For this reason, measures should be taken to evaluate the school as a whole, to increase the interaction between stakeholders and to solve problems (Antle, 2004).

Indicators of students' commitment to school are feeling themselves belonging to the school, accepting themselves as part of the school and having positive feelings about the school (Balkıs, E. Duru, Buluş, & S. Duru, 2011), and in a sense, the students should not feel the need to be elsewhere when they are at school. It is predicted that the strong emotional (Bowlby, 1988) attachment relationship between individuals and people they care about is not only a determinant of childhood, but also a process that affects the individual and the relationships they establish in later life (As cited in Ainsworth, 1989 Altuntaş & Sezer, 2017). Part of the primary effective school life includes adolescence for interacting with society, communication skills, forming peer groups and self-development (Henry & Slater 2007). The sense of attachment to the group, which is an important feeling for social development in adolescents, meets a psychological need (Osterman, 2000). Parents, teachers and friends are important sources of motivation in the lives of adolescents (Yıldırım, 1997). Since students' compliance with school rules will be supported by their friends and teachers, this attitude will positively affect the level of students' school attachment (Karababa., Oral & Dilmaç, 2018). All stakeholders of the school, which they interact with as much as they do, are effective in connecting students to the school. Naturally, the school stands out with the realization of high interaction as the social areas where students live the longest. According to Doğan (2015), like every human being, the student interacts as a social being, especially by communicating with their peers. It interacts with the members of the community in which it lives in order to meet the wishes and expectations of the basic needs of people. As a result of these interactions, they expect to belong to the environment, environment, person and group they live in, to be approved and adopted by them (Yazgan İnanç & Yerlikaya, 2010). Belonging to a group, being connected to its members means meeting the needs of students such as being accepted and supported by their class and school. Therefore, school attachment fosters positive feelings of students towards themselves and contributes to their integration with friends, teachers and other school stakeholders (Sarı & Özgök, 2014). In evaluating each student's education and school background, the quality of the school and their interactions with their friends and teachers should also be taken into account.

Individuals' experiences such as their interactions with their teachers, friends, participation in classes, extracurricular activities, skills and knowledge gained around the school play a big role in their lives. For this reason, the individual's attachment to the school is necessary for his development. For school attachment, students' attendance to classes and school also includes feelings of commitment towards the school. Although the obligation to attend school is provided by legal regulations in our country, this situation has not eliminated the problem of students being connected to the school (Önen, 2014).

Attending or being absent from school is a situation that occurs due to students' subjective attitudes toward school. The developmental period of the children is necessary for the emergence of this situation. According to Koç (2004), for middle school students, there may be a change in feelings and thoughts about school during

adolescence that starts at this school level. It is seen that the changes individuals experience depending on the values formed during this period also affect their education and their feelings towards school. Thanks to the protective feature of the sense of school attachment, students' negative behaviors such as absenteeism are reduced (Nichols, 2008). Especially considering the age and developmental periods of the students, it is important to establish relationships that will support motivation, competence, success, acceptance and support in a positive way (Goodenow, 1992). As a matter of fact, according to Yavuzer (2004), acceptance of children by their friends at this age enables them to gain self-confidence and strengthen their self-worth. Thus, they feel themselves as a part of the school and get away from negative behaviors and establish more positive relationships with their teachers and friends.

School attachment has important consequences for students' school life and future; influences young people's behavior and academic achievement (Hirschi, 2002). School attachment, sense of school belonging (Goodenow, 1991), the popularity of the student among his / her friends at school positively affects their school attachment and learning (Dworkin, 1987). As a psychological need, students' feeling of belonging to a group (Osterman, 2000), being valued and respected within this group increase attachment. Meeting the social needs of students increases their attachment to and belonging to the school. When the motivation for learning is not provided, school attachment weakens. Appreciation of children at school at an early age ensures that they are connected to the school throughout their school life (Goodenow, 1991). Alienation from the school environment reflects negatively on students' behavior. School attachment reduces the negativity of adolescence and increases academic success (Sharkey, You, & Schnoebelen, 2008). Attachment, which emerges mostly in emotional needs during adolescence and can be experienced as sharing feelings with the communicated person, is that adolescents move away from their parents and tend towards their friends (Damarlı, 2006). One of the factors influencing the academic status of students is school attachment (Mouton., et al., 1996). Adolescence is the period in which students experience the most intense psychological and emotional changes. In particular, the awareness of the school administration and teachers of this period, knowing and meeting the individual needs of the students will prevent possible problems by ensuring that they are connected to the school. Academic achievement stands out among students' goals for school. School attachment affects students' academic success and there is a linear relationship between them.

The concepts of school engagement and school attachment are used in the same sense as joining in school-related activities inside the school, valuing the goals of the school, and identifying with the school. Attachment includes an individual's active participation in a task or activity (Fredricks, Blumenfeld, & Paris, 2004) and the behavioral intensity and emotional qualities in this participation process (Reeve et al., 2004). School attachment can also be defined as being related to the school and feeling belonging to the school (Libbey, 2004). According to Covell (2010), attachment includes students' to be in education and training practices and in-school practices, their positive feelings towards their other stakeholders. The concept of school attachment; is considered important in preventing undesirable situations in the school and classroom environment such as students' failure, school drop out rate, alienation, boredom (NRCIM, 2004). School attachment creates an environment where students can express themselves freely and reduces personal anxiety by strengthening social interaction (Hill & Werner, 2006). If psychological needs such as autonomy, belonging, competence are met, school engagement takes place in three different dimensions. These dimensions can be expressed as an affective, behavioral and cognitive attachment (Çengel., Totan, & Çöğmen, 2017). School administrators, teachers, friends and their relationships with other people around the school are effective on the level of students' school attachment. The student's interactions with other people in the school will make him or her feel positive towards the school (Kızılay, 2008).

Practices in education are becoming increasingly widespread with an individual-priority approach (Yıldız & Kılıç, 2020). According to Thompson (2005), environmental factors and stakeholders directly affect the transformation of students in the education and training process. School engagement, which can be expressed as school enjoyment and devotion to the school, is one of the factors required for participation in academic activities and academic development (Fredricks et al., 2004). Education services are offered to individuals in schools as an environment where education is provided that is effective in the development of individuals. The quality of education has a lasting effect on students' interactions and experiences at school, their academic

success and future (Haynes, Emmons & Ben-Avie, 1997). School engagement is associated with a greater appreciation of school and education, greater participation in classroom academic activities (Adelabu, 2007; Cemalcılar, 2010). As school engagement increases, its contribution to the expected behavior development process at school will also increase. It is also seen as an important factor in reducing misbehavior in school (Ünal & Çukur, 2011). According to Bergin & Bergin (2009), some school policies and procedures can facilitate or weaken school attachment. Making interventions throughout the school, providing a different of social activities that students can access, keeping schools small, ensuring the continuity of people and space, facilitating transition to new schools, and ensuring in-and-out transitions affect school attachment. (Furlong & Christenson, 2008). Wehlage et al. (1989) stated that students are affected by the factors of commitment to classmates, compliance with school norms, participation in school activities and reliance in the competence of the school and commitment to education.

School attachment affects students' academic success (Calabrese, 1987). It is seen that negativities such as socio-economic inadequacies, low parental education level, absence from school, family unrest, being a minority, substance use negatively affect students' school attachment and success (McWhirter et al. 1993). It is observed that most of the students who feel deficient in school attachment are unable to focus on studying, the lessons are not interesting, they spend time with friends who are not related to the school (Hupfeld, 2007), low income and students with high academic success have high levels of school attachment (Conchas, 2001). Nowadays, students spend most of their time at school, students are prepared for exams with intensive education programs at all levels from the beginning of their education and training life to the process of having a profession. The priority of families and students is seen as academic success. According to Pereira (2015), Family, relationships with teachers, friendship, personal characteristics, psycho-social processes and school can be determinants in students' academic success (de Castro and Pereira, 2019). School attachment is about success and persistence in school as well as positive academic outcomes (Fredricks, Blumenfeld & Paris, 2004). Supportive teachers and peers in the school context as an open space for students' personal choices contribute to a higher commitment (behavioral, emotional or cognitive) to stimulating and specific tasks.

It is observed that students supported by their peers and encouraged by their teachers who are encouraged by their parents develop their feelings of belonging to the school, love, success, trust and attachment (Özdemir, Yalın & Sezgin, 2008). As students gain confidence in the school, their communication with friends, relationships, and attachment to their teachers and school also increase (Özdemir, Sezgin, Şirin, Karip & Erkan, 2010). Therefore, parents should always support their children, knowing that they will spend a long time at school, to be more interested in them, to feel better in the school environment and to positively affect their sense of school attachment.

The knowledge and skills students gain with education and training environment, their contacts with their friends, to be participate in lesson activities and similar behaviors play a very important role in their future life. In this respect, school and its commitment are important for the individual's multidirectional development (Önen, 2014). That's why it is essential to understand how students' attachment is affected over the years of school (Duy and Yıldız, 2014). School engagement, which contributes to the student's positive behaviors, academic success and etc., is considered very important because it is the key to solving the problems of low achievement, alienation from school, dropout and dropout (Anderson, et al., 2004). As with education' quality, students' life quality at school will turn into a satisfaction that supports their participation in educational activities at school, and will positively affect their behavior towards friends and teachers and their feelings of attachment (Hunt-Sartori, 2007). When the researches are examined, there are different results from each other. The research results show that younger students' level of school attachment is higher than older students; The school attachment level of students with a good family financial situation indicates that the level of school attachment of students with a poor family financial situation is higher. In addition, as the grade level of students increases, the decrease in their level of school attachment indicates that it decreases from primary school to high school. The level of school attachment of students with high academic achievement is higher than the level of students with low academic achievement. School attachment shows that there is a linear and positive relationship between the academic achievements of students with high level of attachment. Successful students see themselves as safe as they adopt the school, and receive love, respect and attention from their friends and

teachers.

In the context of today's educational understanding, school attachment stands out as an important factor especially for students. Accordingly, it would be useful to examine school attachment in terms of children's psychosocial development and to be taken into account in educational research for children of secondary school age. The fact that students with high levels of school attachment are more likely to be academically successful and avoid the hidden dangers of adolescence shows the importance of this study. The purpose of this study is to investigate whether secondary school students' level of school attachment differs according to gender, class level, family income level, academic achievement, parents' age, parents' education level and parents' job variables.

2. Method

Descriptive survey method was used in this study which aims to investigate secondary school students' school attachment in terms of various variables. This method aims to investigate the existing situation. According to Karasar (2003), scanning models are a research approach that aims to describe a past or present situation as it is.

2.1. Participants

The participants of the study are secondary school students studying in Beylikdüzü district of Istanbul. The sample consists of 382 students who were selected by random sampling method in the 5th and 8th grades of a state and a private secondary school in Beylikdüzü district in the 2019-2020 academic year. 211 (55.23%) of the students were female and 171 (44.77%) were male. In the study, an appropriate sampling method was used, which provides convenience in terms of time, money and labor, and is not based on probability, starting from the most accessible unit of the researcher (Büyüköztürk, et al., 2014).

2.2. Instruments

The school attachment level of the students was determined using the "School Attachment Scale for Children and Adolescents" adapted by Savi (2011) into Turkish. At the same time, a "Personal Information Form" was applied to determine the personal characteristics of secondary school students participating in the study.

Findings

The results of the t-test conducted to determine whether the mean scores of the School Attachment Scale for Children and Adolescents differ in terms of gender are given in Table 1.

Table 1: T-Test Results on the Comparison of School Attachment Scale Scores for Children and Adolescents in Terms of Gender

	Gender	N	X	S	sd	t	p																																
Attachment to School	Female	211	4,08	,75	380	-,18	,858																																
	Male	171	4,09	,77				Attachment to teacher	Female	211	3,86	,73	380	-1,93	,055	Male	171	4,00	,68	Attachment to Friends	Female	211	4,43	,54	380	,64	,525	Male	171	4,40	,57	Total	Female	211	4,13	,50	380	-,66	,507
Attachment to teacher	Female	211	3,86	,73	380	-1,93	,055																																
	Male	171	4,00	,68				Attachment to Friends	Female	211	4,43	,54	380	,64	,525	Male	171	4,40	,57	Total	Female	211	4,13	,50	380	-,66	,507	Male	171	4,16	,49								
Attachment to Friends	Female	211	4,43	,54	380	,64	,525																																
	Male	171	4,40	,57				Total	Female	211	4,13	,50	380	-,66	,507	Male	171	4,16	,49																				
Total	Female	211	4,13	,50	380	-,66	,507																																
	Male	171	4,16	,49																																			

$p < .05$

As can be seen from Table 1, school attachment levels of students do not differ significantly according to gender in terms of school attachment, teacher attachment, friend attachment and total scores.

Table 2: ANOVA Results on the Comparison of School Attachment Scale Scores for Children and Adolescents in Terms of Class Level

	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F	p	Significant Difference
Attachment to School	Between Groups	6,943	3	2,314	4,077	,007	6.class-7.class
	In-Group	214,600	378	568			6.class-8.class
	Total	221,543	381				
Attachment to teacher	Between Groups	3,344	3	1,115	2,194	,088	
	In-Group	192,055	378	,508			
	Total	195,399	381				
Attachment to Friends	Between Groups	,848	3	,283	,903	,440	
	In-Group	119,033	380	,313			
	Total	119,882	383				
Total	Between Groups	1,340	3	,447	1,800	,147	
	In-Group	92,779	374	,248			
	Total	94,119	377				

p <.05

As can be seen from Table 2, there is no significant difference among the school attachment levels of students in terms of teacher and friend attachment factors and total score levels. However, according to the results of multiple comparisons between groups, a significant difference is found between the groups in the school attachment factor. According to this result, it is seen that 6th grade students 'level of school attachment is higher than 7th and 8th grade students' level of school attachment.

Table 3: ANOVA Results on the Comparison of School Attachment Scale Scores for Children and Adolescents in Terms of Students' Academic Level

	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F	p	Significant Difference
Attachment to School	Between Groups	,496	3	,165	,282	,838	
	In-Group	218,830	373	,587			
	Total	219,326	376				
Attachment to teacher	Between Groups	2,511	3	,837	1,625	,183	
	In-Group	192,157	373	,515			
	Total	194,668	376				
Attachment to Friends	Between Groups	1,143	3	,381	1,214	,304	
	In-Group	117,734	375	,314			
	Total	118,877	378				
Total	Between Groups	,205	3	,068	,271	,846	
	In-Group	93,100	369	,252			
	Total	93,305	372				

p <.05

As can be seen in Table 3, the level of school attachment does not differ significantly according to the academic achievement of the students in terms of school and teacher and friend attachment factors and total scores.

Table 4: ANOVA Results on the Comparison of School Attachment Scale Scores for Children and Adolescents in Terms of Student's Mother's Age

	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F	p	Significant Difference
Attachment to School	Between Groups	1,977	3	,659	1,139	,333	
	In-Group	217,550	376	,579			
	Total	219,526	379				
Attachment to teacher	Between Groups	,204	3	,068	,131	,941	
	In-Group	195,158	376	,519			
	Total	195,363	379				
Attachment to Friends	Between Groups	,940	3	,313	,996	,395	
	In-Group	118,909	378	,315			
	Total	119,849	381				
Total	Between Groups	,520	3	,173	,692	,557	
	In-Group	93,264	372	,251			
	Total	93,785	375				

p < .05

In Table 4, school attachment levels of students do not differ significantly according to the mother age variable of the students in terms of school attachment, teacher attachment, friend attachment factors and total scores.

Table 5: ANOVA Results on the Comparison of School Attachment Scale Scores for Children and Adolescents in Terms of Students' Father's Age

	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F	p	Significant Difference
Attachment to School	Between Groups	2,167	3	,722	1,277	,282	
	In-Group	210,975	373	,566			
	Total	213,142	376				
Attachment to teacher	Between Groups	,463	3	,154	,302	,824	
	In-Group	190,830	373	,512			
	Total	191,293	376				
Attachment to Friends	Between Groups	1,281	3	,427	1,372	,251	
	In-Group	116,710	375	,311			
	Total	117,991	378				
Total	Between Groups	1,046	3	,349	1,442	,230	
	In-Group	89,185	369	,242			
	Total	90,231	372				

p < .05

In Table 5, school attachment levels of students do not differ significantly according to the father age variable of the students in terms of school attachment, teacher attachment, friend attachment factors and total scores.

Table 6: ANOVA Results on the Comparison of School Attachment Scale Scores for Children and Adolescents in Terms of Students' Mother's Job

	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F	p	Significant Difference
Attachment to School	Between Groups	,154	2	,077	,131	,877	
	In-Group	213,721	365	,586			
	Total	213,875	367				
Attachment to teacher	Between Groups	,952	2	,476	,911	,403	
	In-Group	190,591	365	,522			
	Total	191,543	367				
Attachment to Friends	Between Groups	,012	2	,006	,019	,981	
	In-Group	114,277	367	,311			
	Total	114,289	369				
Total	Between Groups	,067	2	,033	,134	,875	
	In-Group	90,014	361	,249			
	Total	90,081	363				

p < .05

In Table 6, school attachment levels of students do not differ significantly according to the mother's job variable of the students in terms of school and teacher and friend attachment factors and total scores.

Table 7: ANOVA Results on the Comparison of School Attachment Scale Scores for Children and Adolescents in Terms of Students' Father's Job

	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F	p	Significant Difference
Attachment to School	Between Groups	2,458	2	1,229	2,109	,123	
	In-Group	215,548	370	,583			
	Total	218,006	372				
Attachment to teacher	Between Groups	2,096	2	1,048	2,062	,129	
	In-Group	188,098	370	,508			
	Total	190,194	372				
Attachment to Friends	Between Groups	1,444	2	,722	2,306	,101	
	In-Group	116,427	372	,313			
	Total	117,870	374				
Total	Between Groups	1,696	2	,848	3,445	,033	
	In-Group	90,085	366	,246			
	Total	91,781	368				

p < .05

As can be seen in Table 7, there is no significant difference among the school attachment levels of students in terms of school attachment, teacher attachment and friend attachment factors. However, according to the results of multiple comparisons between groups, there is a significant difference in the total score level between the groups. According to this result, it is seen that the students whose fathers are in the other profession group have higher levels of school attachment than the students whose fathers are in the special profession group.

Table 8: ANOVA Results on the Comparison of School Attachment Scale Scores for Children and Adolescents in Terms of Family Income Level of Students

	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F	p	Significant Difference
Attachment to School	Between Groups	2,773	3	,924	1,596	,191	
	In-Group	165,028	285	,579			
	Total	167,801	288				
Attachment to teacher	Between Groups	3,432	3	1,144	2,247	,083	
	In-Group	144,564	284	,509			
	Total	147,997	287				
Attachment to Friends	Between Groups	,507	3	,169	,512	,674	
	In-Group	94,093	285	,330			
	Total	94,600	288				
Total	Between Groups	1,180	3	,393	1,498	,215	
	In-Group	74,052	282	,263			
	Total	75,232	285				

p < .05

As can be seen in Table 8, school attachment levels of students do not differ significantly according to the family income level variable in terms of school and teacher and friend attachment factors and total scores.

Table 9: ANOVA Results on the Comparison of School Attachment Scale Scores for Children and Adolescents in Terms of the Mother's Education Level

	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F	p	Significant Difference
Attachment to School	Between Groups	6,100	4	1,525	2,669	,032	University- Primary School University- High School
	In-Group	215,443	377	,571			
	Total	221,543	381				
Attachment to teacher	Between Groups	1,785	4	,446	,869	,483	
	In-Group	193,613	377	,514			
	Total	195,399	381				
Attachment to Friends	Between Groups	1,383	4	,346	1,106	,354	
	In-Group	118,499	379	,313			
	Total	119,882	383				
Total	Between Groups	2,086	4	,522	2,114	,078	
	In-Group	92,033	373	,247			
	Total	94,119	377				

p < .05

As can be seen from Table 9, there is no significant difference among the school attachment levels of students in terms of teacher and friend attachment factors and total score levels. However, according to the results of multiple comparisons between groups, a significant difference is found between the groups in the school attachment factor. According to this result, it is seen that the level of school attachment of students whose mothers are university graduates is higher than students whose mothers are primary and high school graduates.

Table 10: ANOVA Results on the Comparison of School Attachment Scale Scores for Children and Adolescents in Terms of the Father's Education Level

	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F	p	Significant Difference
Attachment to School	Between Groups	2,095	4	,524	,900	,464	
	In-Group	219,449	377	,582			
	Total	221,543	381				
Attachment to teacher	Between Groups	,866	4	,217	,420	,794	
	In-Group	194,533	377	,516			
	Total	195,399	381				
Attachment to Friends	Between Groups	1,693	4	,423	1,357	,248	
	In-Group	118,188	379	,312			
	Total	119,882	383				
Total	Between Groups	1,059	4	,265	1,061	,375	
	In-Group	93,060	373	,249			
	Total	94,119	377				

p < .05

As can be seen in Table 10, school attachment levels of students do not differ significantly according to the father's education level variable in terms of school attachment, teacher attachment, friend attachment factors and total scores.

4. Discussion

In this study, the school attachment levels of secondary school students were investigated according to demographic variables. In this study, it was determined that the views of secondary school students were similar and there was no significant difference in terms of attachment to school, attachment to teacher, attachment to friend and total scores according to the variables of gender, academic achievement, parents' age, parents' job, family income level and father education level. With this result, when the average scores ($\bar{X}$) of all variables were analyzed, it was determined that all of the scores were above average, they were effective in school attachment and all factors, and increased the level of school attachment.

When the research findings are evaluated; There was no statistically significant difference between male and female students in terms of school attachment. This result is similar to other studies showing that there is no difference in the level of school attachment by gender (Somers and Gizzi, 2001; Wei ve Chen, 2010; Duy and Yıldız, 2014; Altuntaş and Sezer, 2017; Yıldız and Kılıç, 2020). The fact that the academic achievement levels of the students studying at the schools where this study was conducted are medium and above (70-100 points range) causes the groups to show similarities in terms of students' school attachment levels. It is observed that problems such as anxiety, loneliness and absenteeism are low among students with a high level of school attachment, while intrinsic motivation and academic success are high (Cemalcılar, 2010). The most important part of connecting to school is the connection with friends. Students' interaction and communication with each other and with their teachers is very important for education. Because teachers are very effective in the school environment and they affect students at cognitive and affective levels (Wang & Eccles, 2013).

When the opinions of the participant students in the study were investigated, a significant difference was found between the groups in the factor of school attachment according to the level of the class they studied. According to this result, it is seen that the level of school attachment of 6th grade students is higher than the level of school attachment of 7th and 8th grade students. There is no significant difference among the school attachment levels of the students in terms of teacher attachment, friend attachment factors and total score levels. When the literature is examined, it has been determined that school attachment increases as the grade level decreases (Wei & Chen, 2010; Bellici, 2015; Yıldız & Kılıç, 2020).

When the views of the students participating in the study were investigated, a significant difference was found between the groups in the total score levels of the students according to the father's job. According to this result,

it is seen that the students whose fathers are in the other profession group have higher levels of school attachment than the students whose fathers are in the special profession group. There is no significant in terms of school attachment, teacher attachment and friend attachment factors difference among the school attachment levels of students.

When the opinions of the participant students were investigated, a significant difference was found between the groups in the school attachment factor according to the students' mother's education level. According to this result, it is seen that the level of attachment of the students whose mothers graduated to the school is higher than the students whose mothers are primary and high school graduates. There is no significant difference among the school attachment levels of students in terms of teacher attachment, friend attachment factors and total score levels.

It is stated that school attachment has a positive relationship with educational outcomes such as achieving academic success (LeCroy & Krysik, 2008); positive feelings towards school, active participation in different efficiencies at school (Thompson, 2005), and a decrease in the likelihood of committing crimes (Owens-Sabir, 2007) and engaging in risky behaviors. Besides, with the well-being of adolescent and children, decrease in the degree of anxiety, loneliness, school absenteeism in students (Savi, 2011); It also helps to increase autonomy, positive social behavior, intrinsic motivation, and academic achievement (Cemalcılar, 2010). Considering the importance and consequences of school attachment, it can be investigated with students of all age levels at different types of schools and levels, and with different variables.

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